

Teaching Practice: Catalyst for Quality Teacher Production in Nigerian Colleges of Education

Amos A. Akoshi, PhD

*Department of English, School of Languages, College of Education,
Akwanga, Nasarawa State, Nigeria*

Aria John Saleh, PhD ✉

*Department of English, School of Languages, College of Education,
Akwanga, Nasarawa State, Nigeria*

Sabo Ezekiel Saleh, PhD

*Department of Psychology, School of Languages, College of Education,
Akwanga, Nasarawa State, Nigeria*

Abstract

Teaching practice is the name given to the preparation of student teachers for teaching through practical training. It is a cardinal and indispensable aspect of teacher preparation in Nigeria. There must be quality assurance in the preparation of teachers for the new generation. This paper examines the concept of teaching practice, quality assurance in relation to teacher education in Nigeria, importance of teaching practice, strategies for quality assurance, problems and solutions associated with lack of quality in teacher education in Nigeria. Conclusions and recommendations made include: more funds should be allocated to teaching practice exercise and micro teaching laboratory should be well equipped to ascertain quality in the preparation of teachers for the new generation in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Teaching Practice, Teacher Education, Quality Assurance, Preparation of Teachers, Micro-Teaching.*

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Introduction

Education is a key factor for socio-economic and technological progress in any modern society. Teachers have a duty to impart skills, values and knowledge. They need proper training and continuous development to be able to deliver educational services in the most appropriate manner. Therefore, the quality of teachers and their activities should be of paramount concern to educational administrators. Only those who are competent in knowledge and skills have great achievements and success in life. Success in life is all about recognising and taking advantage of the opportunities offered by the help of others or skilled expert tutors. Understanding or acquiring knowledge can be achieved by observing how others do things. In the teaching profession, performance skills acquired through training and long practice are one of the basic assets needed for higher performance among teachers. Beginning teachers or trainee teachers need classroom support to gain skills and confidence. This can be acquired through study and guidance from experienced leaders or experts in the profession. In order to have a disciplined heart and a professional mindset, the younger generation of future teachers needs to be equipped. This can be achieved through thorough supervision. In order to improve the quality of teaching practice and the learning process in schools, supervision, whether internal or external, is an important basic component of teacher education.

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Concept of Teacher Education

Teacher education can be seen as the professional training of teachers to acquire the attitudes, skills and knowledge considered desirable to make them efficient and effective in their work in accordance with the needs of society. It can be described as a cyclical affair in which both content area and pedagogical skills are packaged for student teachers to prepare them to meet the demands of the teaching profession (Jekayinfa, 2001). This package may take the form of a practicum, internship or Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES), and often involves a period of time during which student teachers are placed in schools to teach and practically demonstrate the knowledge and skills they have acquired during their training. Teaching practice is an essential stage in a teacher's professional development. According to Sina, O. & Bello O. A (2014), "it provides an opportunity for student teachers to apply the knowledge and theories learned in their various institutions to the real classroom situation". Teaching practice has been identified as the most challenging, rewarding and important stage in teacher preparation (Goethals & Howard, 2000) and it is generally agreed that it is key to teacher preparation (Guytons & McIntyre, 2010). As a result of the fact that teaching practice is relevant, it should be organised in such a way that student-teachers can continuously acquire current knowledge, skills and develop professionally; proper and adequate supervision of teaching practice should be done to bring about quality assurance in teacher education programmes in Nigeria.

Teaching Practice

Teaching practice is a fundamental component of teacher education, providing student teachers with an essential opportunity to acquire important teaching skills through practical experience in the field. This experience will prepare them for efficiency and effectiveness in teaching after graduation.

Teaching Practice (T.P.) is an essential aspect of the student teacher's professional development. It is a core course in the preparation of teachers in Nigeria. It is conducted in both Colleges of Education, Faculties of Education and Institutes in Nigerian Universities. Teaching practice is monitored internally and externally for quality assurance.

In a teacher education programme, if there is no practice teaching exercise, the process is incomplete and deficient. It is an exercise that is practical for new entrants to the teaching profession. It goes beyond mastering the subject to be taught and knowing how to teach. The purpose of teaching practice is to develop several competencies in the student teacher, which include interpersonal, pedagogical, intercultural and psychological competencies (Zindi; Nyota & Batidzirai, 2005). Student teachers are prepared for teaching practice through micro-teaching course(s), observation of master teachers and peer teaching for quality output during teaching practice.

Various Colleges of Education, Faculties and Institutes of Education use student teachers for student teaching and every effort is made to match students with competent, qualified teachers for supervision. An integral part of student teaching is the supervision and evaluation of student teachers. Supervision is provided through a coordinated partnership between teachers in the school of practice and lecturers in the institutions. In Nigeria, student teachers from Colleges of Education are required to spend one semester of thirteen weeks in their school of practice, while undergraduate students spend six weeks in their school of practice. Supervision of student teachers is the responsibility of both the teacher training institutions and the host school.

In order to have quality teaching in teacher education, supervision should be the critical component of the practice exercise. Inhangbe (2017) has seen supervision in teaching practice exercise which is aimed at providing guidance and holding environment in appropriate professional relationship so that helpful and most effective skills and potent methods for effective teaching and learning are not only engaged, re-engaged, learned and refined but also carefully and properly applied: Teaching practice coupled with effective supervision can improve the standard of education. It can be seen that the teaching practice experience is lacking or has been taken away from those who attended teacher training colleges and

colleges of education in the past. All these teachers have undergone a complete metamorphosis in teaching practice and this has helped them to acquire teaching skills that help them to excel and qualify for teaching.

Objective of Teaching Practice

The National University Commission (NUC, 2007) and the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE, 2015) have highlighted the fundamental objectives of teaching practice exercises.

These are:

1. To expose student-teachers to real life classroom experience under the Supervision of professional teachers.
2. To provide the forum for Student-teacher to translate educational theories and principles into practice.
3. To enable student-teachers discover their Strengths and weaknesses in classroom teaching and provide opportunities to enable them address their weaknesses and enrich their Strengths.
4. To familiarize student-teachers with real school environment as their future work. Place
5. To provide Student teachers with an opportunity for further acquisition of professional Skills, Competencies, personal characteristics and experience for full-time teaching after graduation.
6. To help student-teachers develop a positive attitude towards the teaching profession,
7. To serve as a means of assessing the quality of training being provided by teacher training institutions.
8. To provide student-teachers with opportunity to have a teaching evaluation and to gain constructive criticism.
9. To develop skills in the use of fundamental procedures, techniques and methods of teaching.
10. To enable the student teachers effectively plan and prepare lessons.

In universities and colleges of education, supervision of teaching practice is the most important or integral part of the teacher education process. Gordon (2004) says that supervision is woven into the whole framework and exercise of teaching practice exercise of teacher education either in the universities or colleges of education or other training institutes, the component of supervision wherein education experts are involved in providing guidance and direction for both, the teacher trainee and the whole exercise of both incorporate and provided for standard or quality to surface. Supervision is expected to be involved in the planning, initiation, implementation and completion of the practice.

In the supervision of teaching practice programme in training institutions, some factors beset the quality education. In Nigeria, there are practices that have almost become the norm and which are against or contrary to the basic or minimum expectation of supervision of teaching practice, these are:

1. There is no interactive engagement between the supervisor and the Student Teachers through the whole process.
2. It is the usual practice of supervisor today solely setting the agenda and focus of observation visit
3. fixing of dates and times of supervision without the consent or input and involvement of the student teachers
4. Lack of feedback during and after the observation phase of the process
5. No more post observation phase between the supervisor and supervisee

Importance of Teaching practice in Teacher Education in Nigeria

Teaching practice enhances the professional development of student teachers in the following ways:

1. It provides the time and avenue for student teachers to acquire competencies that are required in their teaching professional development.
2. It brings student teachers into a programme of Cooperative and interactive guidance by experienced teachers (Young & Edward, 2006).
3. Practical experience affords student teachers the opportunity to reflect on their own actions in the classroom and to acquire valuable skills, knowledge and attitude which are required in management of student learning experience in the Classroom (Imogie, 2009).
4. It affords the student teachers the opportunity to reflect not just on matters associated with professional life and growth but also know who they are and are to become in the new generation (De Ville, 2010),
5. It allows student teachers to have ample chance and the real life situations to apply theories and principles of education they have been taught in their institutions (Olaitan & Agusiobo, 2000)
6. It enables the student teachers to become more familiar with variety of instructional materials and resources, evaluate and select those appropriate for the objectives in a teaching unit lesson (Adekunle, 2006)
7. It provides the trainer the opportunity of both assessing and guiding the trainee for both formative and summative evaluation purposes (Afolabi, 2005).
8. It enables the student teachers to organize syllabus contents around major concepts and generalizations in the development of sequential learning in a unit or a course of Study (Adeniran, 2007).

Remodeling Supervision of Teaching practice

The existence of some of the negative practices that challenge the supervision of teaching practice, which invariably affect the quality of teachers, must be addressed. There is need to recognise all these negative effects or challenges facing supervision of teaching practice in Nigeria in order to address these deficiencies for the purpose of achieving the objectives of teaching practice.

The component of supervision as an integral part of the teacher education programme must be set right for the supervision of teaching practice. In order to produce quality and productive teachers, and even to have sustainable and meaningful teacher education, supervision needs to be redesigned, reoriented, committed and well implemented. These are the following ideas or suggestions for the success of the exercise.

1. The approaches to the supervision of the teaching practice in Nigerian institutions must be remodeled and restrategized in order to accommodate new approaches
2. The interaction or contact between the Supervisor and new teachers (neophytes) during teaching practice exercise should be structured to provide the opportunities for them to have their concerns and confusions on issues and theories related to effective engagement of teaching and learning in the real environment
3. To have quality personnel in teaching profession, Supervision of teaching practice should adopt clinical supervision approach where both the Supervisor and the student teacher will be considered equally important with adequate attention.
4. The grades awarded should not be emphasized too much during observation process but the exercise should emphasize the skills and methods of learning engagement.

Concept of Quality Assurance

Quality can be seen as the fulfilment of performance requirements. It is also characterised by the level of excellence in performance on the strength of context, inputs, process and equipment (Onocha, 2002). Quality in relation to education refers to standard or conformance to certain minimum standards (Onuma, 2008), Ojerinde, (2007) viewed quality in education to factors such as well articulated national goals, well planned curriculum at each level, assessment procedures and instruments, capacity for examination data, use of assessment of results and quality of student enrolment.

Quality assurance is the management of goods, services and activities from the input stage through the process to the output stage of production (UBE, 2002). Assurance revolves around meeting certain acceptable criteria of minimum quality standards to be achieved in the production of goods and services.

Quality assurance, which involves the provision and maintenance of the condition, is determined to guarantee a high standard of outcomes and products of teacher education institutions in Nigeria (European Student Handbook, 2005). Quality assurance also uses the services of teacher education to train qualified personnel to enhance their performance in their various workplaces (educational institutions). The philosophical objectives of quality assurance in education is the acceptance or decision of the educational institution to train student teachers' competence in a given discipline Okebukola, (2005) highlighted some factors that contribute to quality assurance in education as follows:

1. Provision of information to public on quality and standards,
2. Credibility to award of certificates,
3. Engendering Confidence in a programme,
4. Ensuring accountability, and
5. Enhancing quality and standards.

In the light of the above, quality assurance in education involves the monitoring of school facilities, the effectiveness and efficiency of teachers, the adequacy and accessibility of facilities and teaching resources needed for effective teaching and learning, and the preparation of teachers to meet the challenges of the new generation and the ever-changing world of today.

Problems and Solutions Associated with lack of Quality in Teacher Education in Nigeria

The following are the problems associated with lack of quality in teacher education in Nigeria:

1. Proliferation of low quality graduates.
2. Low or poor productivity.
3. Poor job performance, the threat occasioned by certification racketeering and qualification inflation.
4. Inadequate numbers and quality of teaching and non-teaching staff (Nwatuluak, 2003).

Nwankwo (2008), highlighted Solutions for ensuring quality assurance in teacher education in Nigeria Viz;

1. Availability of adequate and qualified Staff;
2. Availability of adequate and modern technological facilities,
3. Regular Staff development programmes and supervision and output
4. Continuous appraisal of teacher educational programme and personnel,
5. Adequate planning,

6. Adequate funding of teacher education in Nigeria.

If all these could be applied in all ramifications, there will be quality assurance in teacher preparation for the new generation in Nigeria.

Conclusion

This paper summarises the concept of classroom practice; quality assurance and the importance of classroom practice in the preparation of teachers in Nigeria were extensively discussed. The paper also critically examined supervision as an essential component of teacher education. For instance, the paper suggested that supervision of teaching practice needs to be reviewed. That the technique of supervision should be strictly adhered to. It also suggested that adequate supervision facilities should be provided at all costs. The government should provide funds at appropriate times. The commitment of the supervisor is essential and needs to be emphasised as clinical supervision is very useful. Problems and solutions related to the lack of quality teacher education in Nigeria were also highlighted and discussed.

Recommendations

In order to enhance quality in the preparation of teachers for the new generation, the following recommendations should be looked into by all stakeholders in preparation of teachers in Nigeria:

1. Workshops on teaching practice supervision by the training institutions should be organized regularly for all supervisors to clarify issues that will affect quality of teaching practice supervision such as proper interpretation, supervision instruments so that there is supervision consensus in dealing with similar student issues and supervisor bias is checked.
2. More incentives should be provided by the committee organizing teaching practice to the supervisors
3. Provision of new Information and Communication Technologies facilities should be used to train the student teachers as this will enable them to meet the global challenges of the new generation.
4. Adequate monitoring of the entire educational System should be carried out regularly and reports should be submitted to appropriate quarters for adequate implementation.
5. All teacher training institutions should have a well equipped micro-teaching laboratory where students will be exposed to the rudiments of teaching before the actual teaching
6. More funds should be allocated for the preparation and running of teaching practice exercise so as to enhance quality.
7. Supervisors should endeavour to visit the student teachers regularly and, in good time to supervise the actual teaching process.

All hands must be on deck during teaching exercise to enhance quality assurance in the Preparation of teachers for the new generation in Nigeria.

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